

Energy-Efficient Transmission Rate Selection and Power Control for Relay-Assisted Device-to-Device Communications Underlying Cellular Networks

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Abstract—Device-to-device (D2D) communication underlying cellular networks is seen as a promising technology for future communication systems, especially when relays are employed to extend the range of D2D links. However, the mutual interference between the spectrum-sharing D2D links and conventional cellular (CC) links is still the dominating performance limiting factor, which enforces those links to adopt higher transmission power and consequently reduces the battery lifetime of user equipment (UE). As energy saving is always one of the key concerns, we propose to minimize the total transmission energy consumption of a relay-assisted D2D link and a CC link sharing radio resources by jointly optimizing their transmission rate selection and power control (TRSPC). We formulate the optimization problem as a non-convex non-linear programming (NLP) problem and then develop a game theory based distributed approach to solve it. Simulation results demonstrate that our game theory based TRSPC approach can enormously decrease the total transmission energy consumption compared with existing works.

Index Terms—relay-assisted D2D communication, transmission rate selection, power control, transmission energy consumption.

I. INTRODUCTION

DEVICE-to-device (D2D) communication underlying cellular networks has been seen as a promising technology in 5G mobile networks to enhance the spectral efficiency, offload traffic from base stations (BSs), and reduce the transmission delay for user equipment (UE) [1]. If a direct D2D link is not favorable, then cooperative relays may be further employed to enhance the quality and range of this link [2].

An important issue in fully exploiting the merits of D2D communications is the careful control of the mutual interference between the D2D links and the conventional cellular (CC) links that share radio resources. Interference control approaches for single-hop D2D communications were well studied in [3]-[6]. However, these approaches can not be applied directly in relay-assisted D2D communication scenarios, where the two-hop D2D transmissions make the mutual interference between D2D and CC links more complex.

There have been some initial efforts in developing interference control solutions for relay-assisted D2D communications. The relay selection, resource allocation, and power control schemes were proposed in [7]-[9], respectively. Nevertheless, in these schemes, the two hops of a relay-assisted D2D link are simply assumed to have equal durations and the same transmission rate, which ignored the potentially different channel conditions between the two D2D hops and may lead to degraded performance of interference control.

In this work, we study the interference control problem for a relay-assisted D2D link and a CC link sharing the same

radio resources in a more realistic system where different transmission rates may be selected for the two D2D hops according to their channel conditions.

The mutual interference between the D2D link and the CC link will enforce them to adopt higher transmission power and consequently produce larger interference to each other. As energy saving is always one of the key concerns, we propose to minimize the total transmission energy consumption of the relay-assisted D2D link and CC link by jointly optimizing their transmission rate selection and power control (TRSPC). Subject to the end-to-end transmission delay and transmission data volume requirements of each link, we formulate the TRSPC problem into a non-convex non-linear programming (NLP) problem, which is hard to solve directly. In view of this, we propose a game theory based distributed TRSPC approach where each link tries to minimize its own energy consumption in the presence of the other link's interference. Performance of the proposed approach is evaluated through simulations.

II. SYSTEM MODEL AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

As the BS usually has a greater capability in interference management than UEs, we assume that the D2D link only reuse the uplink (UL) radio resource [4]. We consider a single cell system with one BS located at the center of the cell. The cell has a circle coverage with the radius of R_{cell} , where we assume that the interference from other cells is mitigated via inter-cell interference coordination [7]. A relay-assisted D2D link and a UL CC link share a UL subchannel, which has the bandwidth of B and can not be reused by other links.

Fig. 1 illustrates an example of a relay-assisted D2D link sharing a UL subchannel with a UL CC link. The subchannel has the bandwidth of B and can not be reused by any other links. The UL CC UE and the D2D source are uniformly distributed in the cell. The D2D destination is uniformly distributed in an annular region and its distance to the D2D source is in the range of $(R_{D2D}, 2 \cdot R_{D2D}]$, where R_{D2D} is the maximum direct transmission distance between two UEs. The relay of the D2D link is in the yellow region, where both its distances to the source and to the destination are not longer than R_{D2D} . The system has one control channel to exchange control messages between the two links. The relay is considered to be an energy-limited mobile UE [2] which works in a half-duplex method. The two hops of the D2D link transmit in the same subchannel. The D2D peer discovery, relay selection, and subchannel allocation are out of our scope.

Different from existing works, we allow the source-to-relay hop and the relay-to-destination hop of the D2D link to have different values of transmission duration. Accordingly, the two hops may have unequal transmission rates and transmission power. We use variables t_{cc} , $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$, and $t_{d2d}^{(2)}$ to denote the

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This work was supported in part by the EU's H2020 Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement No. 778305 and 843401.

Fig. 1. A relay-assisted D2D link sharing a UL subchannel with a UL CC link

transmission time of the CC link and the D2D link's first and second hops, respectively, and use p_{cc} , $p_{d2d}^{(1)}$ and $p_{d2d}^{(2)}$ to denote the transmission power of the CC link and the D2D link during its two hops, respectively. The transmission energy consumption of each link is given by:

$$E_{cc} = p_{cc} \cdot t_{cc} \quad (1)$$

$$E_{d2d} = p_{d2d}^{(1)} \cdot t_{d2d}^{(1)} + p_{d2d}^{(2)} \cdot t_{d2d}^{(2)} \quad (2)$$

We use variables r_{cc} , $r_{d2d}^{(1)}$, and $r_{d2d}^{(2)}$ to denote the transmission rate requirements of the CC link and the D2D link in the two hops, respectively. We consider the worst interference scenario where the CC link may cause mutual interference with both the two hops of the D2D link. With the objective of minimizing the total transmission energy consumption of both links, the optimization problem is formulated as follows:

$$\arg \min_{p_{cc}, p_{d2d}^{(1)}, p_{d2d}^{(2)}, r_{cc}, r_{d2d}^{(1)}, r_{d2d}^{(2)}, t_{cc}, t_{d2d}^{(1)}, t_{d2d}^{(2)}} (E_{cc} + E_{d2d}) \quad (3)$$

s.t.:

$$r_{cc} \cdot t_{cc} \geq V_{cc} \quad (4)$$

$$r_{d2d}^{(i)} \cdot t_{d2d}^{(i)} \geq V_{d2d}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (5)$$

$$B \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{g_{cc} \cdot p_{cc}}{N_0 + g_{d2d,cc}^{(i)} \cdot p_{d2d}^{(i)}} \right) \geq r_{cc}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (6)$$

$$B \cdot \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{g_{d2d}^{(i)} \cdot p_{d2d}^{(i)}}{N_0 + g_{cc,d2d}^{(i)} \cdot p_{cc}} \right) \geq r_{d2d}^{(i)}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (7)$$

$$t_{cc} \leq T \quad (8)$$

$$t_{d2d}^{(1)} + t_{d2d}^{(2)} \leq T \quad (9)$$

$$t_{cc}, t_{d2d}^{(i)}, r_{cc}, r_{d2d}^{(i)}, p_{cc}, p_{d2d}^{(i)} \geq 0, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (10)$$

$$p_{cc}, p_{d2d}^{(i)} \leq p_{max}, \quad i = 1, 2 \quad (11)$$

where V_{cc} and V_{d2d} are the data volumes required to be transmitted by the CC link and the D2D link, respectively, g_{cc} is the channel power gain of the CC link, $g_{d2d}^{(1)}$, $g_{d2d}^{(2)}$ are the channel power gains of the D2D link in the first and second hops, respectively, $g_{cc,d2d}^{(1)}$, $g_{cc,d2d}^{(2)}$, $g_{d2d,cc}^{(1)}$ and $g_{d2d,cc}^{(2)}$ are the channel power gains of the interfering links from the UL CC UE to the D2D relay, from the UL CC UE to the D2D destination, from the D2D source to the BS, and from the D2D relay to the BS, respectively, N_0 is the additive noise power, T is the maximum allowed end-to-end transmission delay of the D2D link and the CC link, and p_{max} is the maximum transmission power of an UE.

We assume a quasi-static channel model where during the transmission periods of the two links, all the channel power gains are constant. $g_{d2d}^{(1)}$, $g_{d2d}^{(2)}$, $g_{cc,d2d}^{(1)}$ and $g_{cc,d2d}^{(2)}$ are

calculated as $d^{-2} \cdot |h|^2$, where d is the distance between the transmitter and the receiver, h is a complex Gaussian channel coefficient following $h \sim CN(0, 1)$. While g_{cc} , $g_{d2d,cc}^{(1)}$ and $g_{d2d,cc}^{(2)}$ are calculated as $d^{-2} \cdot |h|^2 \cdot G_{BS}$, where G_{BS} represents the receiving antenna gain of the BS.

Constraints (4) and (5) require that the transmission rates of both the two links should be large enough to satisfy the data volumes required to be transmitted. Constraints (6) and (7) require that the signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR) for each link should exceed a certain value to guarantee the transmission rate according to Shannon's theory. Constraints (8) and (9) imply that the total transmission time of the two links can not exceed the maximum allowed end-to-end transmission delay. Constraints (10) and (11) require that all the variables are non-negative and the transmission power should not exceed the maximum allowed value.

III. GAME THEORY BASED APPROACH

The optimization problem in (3) is an NLP problem, which is difficult to solve directly. To tackle it, we develop a game theory based distributed approach. Considering the UL CC link and the relay-assisted D2D link as non-cooperative players, we define $\mathbf{s}_{cc} = (p_{cc}, t_{cc}, r_{cc})$ and $\mathbf{s}_{d2d} = (p_{d2d}^{(1)}, p_{d2d}^{(2)}, t_{d2d}^{(1)}, t_{d2d}^{(2)}, r_{d2d}^{(1)}, r_{d2d}^{(2)})$ as the strategies of the CC player and the D2D player, respectively. Each player (link) wants to minimize its own energy consumption subject to its transmission data volume requirement. Thus, the utility function of the CC player or the D2D player is defined as:

$$u_{cc}(\mathbf{s}_{cc} | \mathbf{s}_{d2d}) = \begin{cases} -E_{cc}, & (4, 6, 8, 10, 11) \text{ are reached} \\ \text{null}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

$$u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d} | \mathbf{s}_{cc}) = \begin{cases} -E_{d2d}, & (5, 7, 9 \sim 11) \text{ are reached} \\ \text{null}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

A. Best Response of the CC Player

We can prove the following **Lemma**:

Lemma 1: For given transmission data volume, V , transmission bandwidth, B , channel power gain, g , and total power of interference plus noise at the receiver, P_{IN} , a link's minimum transmission power, p_{min} , is determined by the transmission time, t , while the minimum transmission energy needed, $E_{min}(t)$, is a monotonously decreasing function of t .

Proof. According to (4) and (5), a link's minimum transmission rate requirement can be calculated as:

$$r_{min} = V/t \quad (14)$$

Also, since the value of the left part in (6) or (7) increases monotonously as the transmission power gets larger, the minimum possible transmission power of the link is:

$$p_{min} = (2^{r_{min}/B} - 1) \cdot \frac{P_{IN}}{g} = (2^{\frac{V}{B \cdot t}} - 1) \cdot \frac{P_{IN}}{g} \quad (15)$$

Thus, the link's minimum transmission energy needed is:

$$E_{min}(t) = p_{min} \cdot t = \frac{P_{IN}}{g} \cdot t \cdot (2^{\frac{V}{B \cdot t}} - 1) \quad (16)$$

The first-order derivative and the second-order derivative of $E_{min}(t)$ about t can be calculated as (17) and (18). Obviously, $\frac{d(E_{min}(t))}{d(t)} \rightarrow 0$ when $t \rightarrow +\infty$ and $\frac{d^2(E_{min}(t))}{d(t)^2} > 0$ when t is positive. Thus, we have $\frac{d(E_{min}(t))}{d(t)} < 0$ when $t > 0$. So $E_{min}(t)$ is a monotonously decreasing function of t as the transmission time must be positive. \square

$$\frac{d(E_{min}(t))}{d(t)} = \frac{P_{IN}}{g} \cdot (2^{\frac{V}{B \cdot t}} - 1) - \frac{P_{IN} \cdot V \cdot \ln 2}{g \cdot B} \cdot \frac{2^{\frac{V}{B \cdot t}}}{t} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{d^2(E_{min}(t))}{d(t)^2} = \frac{P_{IN} \cdot V^2 \cdot \ln^2 2}{g \cdot B^2} \cdot \frac{2^{\frac{V}{B \cdot t}}}{t^3} \quad (18)$$

Given the D2D player's strategy, \mathbf{s}_{d2d} , the CC player will try to find the best response strategy which maximizes its own utility function. Considering the worst interference scenario, the largest power of interference signal plus noise of the CC link, $P_{IN,cc}$, equals $\max\{g_{d2d,cc}^{(1)} \cdot p_{d2d}^{(1)}, g_{d2d,cc}^{(2)} \cdot p_{d2d}^{(2)}\} + N_0$. Based on **Lemma 1**, the CC player will achieve the maximum utility function when it has the longest transmission time ($t_{cc} = T$ according to (8)). Thus, according to (14) and (15), the best strategy of the CC player is:

$$\mathbf{s}_{cc}^* = (p_{cc} = (2^{\frac{V_{cc}}{B \cdot T}} - 1) \cdot \frac{P_{IN,cc}}{g_{cc}}, t_{cc} = T, r_{cc} = \frac{V_{cc}}{T}) \quad (19)$$

B. Best Response of the D2D Player

When the CC player's strategy, \mathbf{s}_{cc} , is given, the power of interference signal plus noise at the first and the second hops of the D2D link, $P_{IN,d2d}^{(1)}$ and $P_{IN,d2d}^{(2)}$, will be $N_0 + g_{cc,d2d}^{(1)} \cdot p_{cc}$ and $N_0 + g_{cc,d2d}^{(2)} \cdot p_{cc}$, respectively. Based on **Lemma 1**, the two hops of the D2D link will try to prolong their transmission time to reduce their transmission energy. So in order to maximize $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$, we have (20) and can further prove the following **Lemma**:

$$t_{d2d}^{(1)} + t_{d2d}^{(2)} = T \quad (20)$$

Lemma 2: The feasible region of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ is a closed interval and $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ is a concave function of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ in the feasible region.

Proof. According to (15) in **Lemma 1**, the minimum possible transmission power of the D2D link at the first and the second hops can be calculated as:

$$p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)}) = (2^{\frac{V_{d2d}}{B \cdot t_{d2d}^{(1)}}} - 1) \cdot \frac{P_{IN,d2d}^{(1)}}{g_{d2d}^{(1)}} \quad (21)$$

$$p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)}) = [2^{\frac{V_{d2d}}{B \cdot (T - t_{d2d}^{(1)})}} - 1] \cdot \frac{P_{IN,d2d}^{(2)}}{g_{d2d}^{(2)}} \quad (22)$$

Obviously, $p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)})$ is a decreasing function of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ while $p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)})$ is an increasing function of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$. If $p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d}^{(1),min}) = p_{max}$ and $p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d}^{(1),max}) = p_{max}$, the feasible region of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ is given by $[\max(0, t_{d2d}^{(1),min}), \min(T, t_{d2d}^{(1),max})]$.

Thus, in the feasible region of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$, $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ can be calculated as:

$$u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc}) = -p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)}) \cdot t_{d2d}^{(1)} - p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d}^{(1)}) \cdot (T - t_{d2d}^{(1)}) \quad (23)$$

The second-order derivative of $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ about $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ is calculated as (24). Transparently, in $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$'s feasible region, the second-order derivative of $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ is always negative. So $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ is a concave function of $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$. \square

Based on **Lemma 2**, we can conclude that the D2D player's best strategy can be achieved either when $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ is at the boundaries of its feasible region or when the derivative of $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ about $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ equals zero. Moreover, when

Algorithm 1 : Best response for the relay-assisted D2D player

- 1: input the strategy of the CC player, \mathbf{s}_{cc} ;
- 2: find $t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}$, which makes $\frac{d(u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc}))}{d(t_{d2d}^{(1)})}(t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}) = 0$, in $[0, T]$, using one-dimensional searching method;
- 3: **if** $p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}) > p_{max}$ **then**
- 4: find $t_{d2d,min}^{(1)}$ in $[t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}, T]$, which makes $p_{min,d2d}^{(1)}(t_{d2d,min}^{(1)}) = p_{max}$. and set $t_{d2d}^{(1)} = t_{d2d,min}^{(1)}$;
- 5: **else**
- 6: **if** $p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}) > p_{max}$ **then**
- 7: find $t_{d2d,max}^{(1)}$ in $[0, t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}]$, which makes $p_{min,d2d}^{(2)}(t_{d2d,max}^{(1)}) = p_{max}$, and set $t_{d2d}^{(1)} = t_{d2d,max}^{(1)}$;
- 8: **else**
- 9: set $t_{d2d}^{(1)} = t_{d2d,inf}^{(1)}$;
- 10: **end if**
- 11: **end if**
- 12: calculate $t_{d2d}^{(2)}, r_{d2d}^{(1)}, r_{d2d}^{(2)}, p_{d2d}^{(1)}, p_{d2d}^{(2)}$ using (20), (14), (21), and (22), respectively, and then set \mathbf{s}_{d2d}^* ;

$t_{d2d}^{(1)} \rightarrow 0$ or $t_{d2d}^{(1)} \rightarrow T$, $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ in (23) will approach negative infinity. Thus, the inflection point of $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$ where $u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc})$'s derivative about $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ equals zero must be in the interval of $[0, T]$. We propose **Algorithm 1** to calculate the D2D player's best response given \mathbf{s}_{cc} .

$$\frac{d^2(u_{d2d}(\mathbf{s}_{d2d}|\mathbf{s}_{cc}))}{d(t_{d2d}^{(1)})^2} = -\frac{P_{IN,d2d}^{(1)} \cdot V_{d2d}^2 \cdot \ln^2 2}{g_{d2d}^{(1)} \cdot B^2} \cdot \frac{2^{\frac{V_{d2d}}{B \cdot t_{d2d}^{(1)}}}}{(t_{d2d}^{(1)})^3} - \frac{P_{IN,d2d}^{(2)} \cdot V_{d2d}^2 \cdot \ln^2 2}{g_{d2d}^{(2)} \cdot B^2} \cdot \frac{2^{\frac{V_{d2d}}{B \cdot (T - t_{d2d}^{(1)})}}}}{(T - t_{d2d}^{(1)})^3} \quad (24)$$

C. Implementation of the TRSPC Game

Before data transmission starts, both the CC link and the D2D link are set to work in the control channel and participate in the TRSPC game as non-cooperative players. These two links (players) will be given initial strategies and then adjust their strategies iteratively in a distributed manner. In each iteration of the TRSPC game, every player sends its current strategy to the other player through the control channel. The CC player and D2D player then calculate their best responses using (19) and **Algorithm 1**, respectively, to maximize their own utility functions as defined in (12) and (13), respectively. The best response will be the player's new strategy and will be sent to the other player in the following iteration. The TRSPC game keeps running until it reaches a **Nash equilibrium** [4] or its iteration number reaches a threshold, N_{thd} . Then, the two links start to transmit data in the shared subchannel using the strategies determined through the TRSPC game.

Proposition 1: The Nash equilibrium exists in the proposed TRSPC game.

Proof. According to (15), the minimum possible transmission power of the CC link is a decreasing function of t_{cc} . If $p_{min,cc}(t_{cc,min}) = p_{max}$, the feasible region of t_{cc} is given by $[t_{cc,min}, T]$, which is a nonempty compact convex subset of a Euclidean space. Based on (16) and (18) in **Lemma 1**, the CC player's utility function is continuous and concave about t_{cc} . Similarly, based on **Lemma 2**, the D2D player's utility function is continuous and concave about $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$ and $t_{d2d}^{(1)}$'s feasible region is a nonempty compact convex subset

TABLE I
SIMULATION PARAMETERS

R_{cell}	167 m	R_{D2D}	20 m	B	180 KHz
G_{BS}	30 dB	N_0	10^{-6} W	p_{max}	250 mW
T	0.5 ms	N_{thd}	10		

Fig. 2. Total transmission energy consumption versus μ , where μ is the ratio of the source-to-relay distance and the relay-to-destination distance.

of a Euclidean space. As any concave function must be quasi-concave, the Nash equilibrium exists in the TRSPC game. \square

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

We evaluate the performance of the proposed game theory based approach through simulation. We compare our approach with the approach in [7], where the relay-assisted D2D link has equal values of duration for its two hops and the CC link only transmits in one hop which makes the total transmission energy consumption smaller, and the approach in [9], where the relay-assisted D2D link has equal durations for its two hops and the CC link adopts a fixed transmission rate in T .

In each test, V_{cc} and V_{d2d} are uniformly distributed in $[0, V_{max}]$. We use parameter μ to denote the ratio of the source-to-relay distance to the relay-to-destination distance for the D2D link. The energy consumption of control information exchanging is ignored as the data amounts of the D2D link and the UL CC link are much larger than that of control information. The simulation parameters are summarized in **Table 1** according to 3GPP-LTE IP based systems [1].

Fig. 2 shows the total transmission energy consumption achieved by the three approaches versus the value of μ when $V_{max} = 400$ bits. The energy consumption of the approach in [9] increases rapidly with μ moving away from 1. This is because when the two hops of the D2D link have more different transmission distances, the difference in channel conditions between the two hops will get larger and thus adopting the same transmission rate in the two hops for the D2D link will cause greater mutual interference with the CC link. The energy consumption of the approach in [7] remains relatively high and decreases a little when μ moves away from 1. This is because in [7], the CC link only causes mutual interference with one of the two hops of the D2D link and the mutual interference will descend if the channel condition of this hop rises when μ moves away from 1 and this hop's transmission distance gets shorter. However, according to **Lemma 1**, the CC link in [7]'s approach will consume relatively large energy since its short duration ($T/2$). We can see that our approach always achieves the lowest energy consumption and its energy consumption is less influenced by the variation of μ .

Fig. 3. Total transmission energy consumption versus V_{max} , which is the maximum data volume for both the UL CC link and the D2D link.

Fig. 3 plots the total transmission energy consumption versus V_{max} with μ equalling 2. From Fig. 3, we can see the energy consumption achieved by the three approaches increases rapidly when V_{max} gets larger. This is in accordance with the Shannon's theory. Similar with Fig. 2, results in Fig. 3 also indicate that our approach always achieves the lowest energy consumption. When $V_{max}=500$ bits, our approach can reduce the energy consumption by 47% and 72%, respectively, if it is compared with the approaches in [7] and [9].

V. CONCLUSION

This letter has investigated the TRSPC problem for a relay-assisted D2D link underlying a UL CC link with the goal of minimizing the total transmission energy consumption of the two links. We have formulated the optimization problem as an NLP and proposed a game theory based approach to solve it. We have proven the existence of Nash equilibrium in our TRSPC game and developed methods to calculate each player's best response. Simulation results show that our approach can reduce the total transmission energy consumption evidently as compared to two existing approaches in typical cellular network scenarios.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Zulhasnine, C. Huang, and A. Srinivasan, "Efficient resource allocation for device-to-device communication underlying LTE network," IEEE Conf. Wireless and Mobile Comput., Netw. and Commun., 2010.
- [2] N. Mastrorade, V. Patel, J. Xu, L. Liu, and M. V. D. Schaar, "To relay or not to relay: learning device-to-device relaying strategies in cellular networks," IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput., vol. 15, no. 6, pp. 1569-1585, Jun. 2016.
- [3] Y. Chen, B. Ai, Y. Niu, K. Guan, and Z. Han, "Resource allocation for device-to-device communications underlying heterogeneous cellular networks using coalitional Games," IEEE Trans. Wireless Commun., vol. 17, no. 6, pp. 4163-4176, Jun. 2018.
- [4] Z. Zhang, Y. Wu, X. Chu, and J. Zhang, "Resource allocation and power control for D2D communications to prolong the overall system survival time of mobile cells," IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 17111-17124, Jan. 2019.
- [5] Z. Zhou, M. Dong, K. Ota, G. Wang, and L. T. Yang, "Energy-efficient resource allocation for D2D communications underlying cloud-RAN-based LTE-A networks," IEEE Internet of Things Journal, vol. 3, no. 3, pp. 428-438, Jun. 2016.
- [6] Z. Zhou, K. Ota, M. Dong, and C. Xu, "Energy-efficient matching for resource allocation in D2D enabled cellular networks," IEEE Trans. Vehicular Tech., vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 5256-5268, Jun. 2017.
- [7] R. Tang, J. Zhao, H. Qu, Z. Zhu, and Y. Zhang, "Joint mode selection and resource allocation for mobile relay-aided device-to-device communication," Trans. Internet and Inf. Sys., vol. 10, no. 3, pp. 950-975, Mar. 2016.
- [8] R. Wang, D. Cheng, G. Zhang, Y. Lu, J. Yang, L. Zhao, and K. Yang, "Joint relay selection and resource allocation in cooperative device-to-device communications," AEU-International Journal of Elec. and Commun., vol. 73, pp. 50-58, Mar. 2017.
- [9] C. Gao, Y. Li, Y. Zhao, and S. Chen, "A two-level game theory approach for joint relay selection and resource allocation in network coding assisted D2D communications," IEEE Trans. Mobile Comput., vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 2697-2711, Oct. 2017.
- [10] Z. Zhang, Y. Wu, X. Chu, and J. Zhang, "Resource allocation and power control to maximize the overall system survival time for mobile cells with a D2D underlay," IEEE Commun. Lett., vol. 23, no. 5, pp. 880-883, May 2019.